

The NASE
Proposal for the
International
Day of Light
May, 16th

4° Bridges between Cultures

Messier Challenge

Editors: Beatriz García & Rosa M. Ros

CONICET, UTN-FRM, Politecnico University of
Catalonia and Municipality of Malargüe

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Prologue

"The Starry Sky, Intangible Heritage of Humanity"

In an increasingly urban and technological world, it is easy to forget the beauty and solemnity of the night sky. However, UNESCO has recognized the starry sky as an intangible cultural heritage of humanity, highlighting its cultural and scientific importance. In this context, the NASE Program joins the celebration of the International Day of Light, inviting the global community to rediscover the night sky, and Malargüe was part of it.

Through an innovative proposal, the educational community (students, parents, and teachers) and the general public were encouraged to observe and study the extended or multiple celestial objects selected from the Messier Catalogue, thus promoting curiosity and interest in astronomy.

This initiative, which raises awareness about the importance of protecting our celestial heritage, allowed us to reconnect with nature through the observation and study of the night sky and reflect on our place in the universe.

In the following pages, the results of this initiative are presented, which involved thousands of people from all over the world. We hope that this experience has been enriching and inspires further exploration of the night sky and its secrets.

As the Mayor of the Municipality of Malargüe, I hope we continue to be part of such initiatives. I congratulate those who participated in this project at both the international and local levels and encourage them to keep deepening activities like this that bring science closer to the community.

Warm greetings to all,

Cdor. Celso A. Jaque
Mayor
Municipality of Malargüe

Welcome

Beatriz García & Rosa M. Ros

CONICET-Universidad Tecnológica Nacional, Mendoza, Argentina
Universidad Politécnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain

Welcome to the fourth edition of “Bridges between Cultures”, an initiative of the Network for Astronomy School Education (NASE) on the occasion of UNESCO's International Day of Light - March 16. In 2024, the invitation was to reconnect with the night sky, based on the recognition of extended celestial objects, such as nebulae, clusters and galaxies, from those that are part of the Messier Catalog.

It should be remembered that the starry sky, and all its wonders, has been declared intangible heritage of humanity by UNESCO, in its declaration of La Palma, in 2007¹.

We humans have the responsibility to protect this heritage, which has inspired generations over the millennia, and to do so we must rescue the ancient practice of raising our eyes to the sky.

This proposal allowed experienced observers, amateurs and even those new to the possibility of recognizing celestial objects, to exchange knowledge, information, share experiences and even instruments to improve detection, recognize that the human eye is a powerful optical detector and many of the objects proposed for observation are detectable without the aid of astronomical devices and, above all, it allowed thousands of people fascinated by astronomy to unite behind a global and inclusive project.

We would like to thank the thousands of people who supported the proposal and the institutions that endorsed the project.

We invite you to review a summary of the topics that were discussed throughout the year and the conclusions of the proposal, in the texts prepared by its protagonists.

¹ Declaracion de La Palma, UNESCO, 2007 - https://www.fundacionstarlight.org/docs/files/32_declaracion-sobre-la-defensa-del-cielo-nocturno.pdf

Messier Challenge: the NASE proposal for the IDL-16M in 2024

Beatriz García¹, Rosa M. Ros², Ricardo Moreno³

1. CONICET, Universidad Tecnológica Nacional-FRM, Mendoza, Argentina
2. Universidad Politécnica de Cataluña, Barcelona, Spain
3. Colegio Retamar, Madrid, Spain

Abstract

To commemorate the International Day of Light convened by UNESCO on an annual basis, the NASE Program proposes every year to carry out a simple experience, of educational interest, that allows sharing an activity that involves research and experimentation. The invitation proposes to work between equinoxes and close the year of work with a global, hybrid event. In 2024 and after several editions of experiences that can be carried out in the laboratory of educational establishments, with elements from the same (such as prisms and thermometers) or in controlled conditions during the day (such as determining the latitude from measuring the height of the Sun), it invites us to raise our eyes to the starry night and discover the "jewels" that are found in the sky. The invitation was for the rediscovery of the night sky from the observation of extended or multiple celestial objects, such as clusters, galaxies, nebulae, with or without instruments, selected from the Messier Catalog.

...Pero, hasta ese momento faltaba un ser vivo
de naturaleza más divina
y de mente profunda, más capaz,
que pudiera dominar sobre los otros.
Entonces, nació el hombre.
A éste, o bien lo hizo con una semilla divina
aquel creador de la vida, origen de un mundo mejor,
o bien la tierra recién creada,
apartada no hacía mucho del alto éter
retenía las semillas de su vástago, el cielo;
y ésta, mezclada con las aguas pluviales,
fue moldeada por Prometeo, el hijo de Japeto,
a imagen y semejanza de los dioses que gobiernan todo.
Y, mientras los otros seres vivos miraban hacia la tierra,
concedió al hombre una cabeza erguida
y le ordenó ver hacia el cielo y levantar el rostro a las estrellas.

Ovidio, Metamorfosis. 8dC, Trad. Rita Lilia García Cerezo

1. Introduction

The 2024 NASE [1] proposal for the celebration of the International Day of Light was related to sky observation based on a selection of Messier objects, to which others were added, primarily visible from the Southern Hemisphere. It is important to mention that the selection of Messier Objects [2] was mainly focused on those visible in both hemispheres, and in the case of Southern Hemisphere objects, the criteria followed were those of the NASE coordination group, ensuring that there were objects easily detectable with the naked eye, others faint but reachable with binoculars, and only a few for which a telescope would be the best option.

The invitation to be part of the proposal was extended between March 20 and September 23, 2024, and participants were required to submit photographs or drawings of the observed objects along with a ranking of objects that, according to their criteria, should be included in the NASE Catalog for Schools. These objects were presented in a special form along with the table where the votes were recorded [3].

2. The proposal

NASE, in cooperation with UNESCO, invited people to raise their eyes to the starry night and discover the "gems" found in the "toolbox" we know as the Messier Catalog, in an invitation that includes the discovery of non-stellar celestial objects detectable even without instruments, the location of these objects in the celestial sphere using NASE tools, and sharing the stories the sky tells us or inspires in us.

The French astronomer Charles Messier (1730-1817) (Fig. 1a) [4] discovered more than a dozen comets, and through his observational work, he distinguished these objects from others, such as faint ones (like nebulae) or extended ones formed by stars (like clusters or galaxies). In doing so, he created a list of objects he discovered that appeared to be comets but were not. The compilation of this list, along with Pierre Méchain, is known as the "Messier Catalog." It is one of the most famous lists of astronomical objects, and many of the objects included in it are still referenced by their Messier number.

The Messier list of objects (Fig. 1b) was originally published in 1771 and included only 45 objects; in 1774, Messier himself completed it by adding up to 103 objects. Other astronomers used Messier's notes to finally complete the list with 110 objects, as we know it today.

This catalog was compiled by European astronomers from Central Europe, which is why there are no objects below a declination of 35° South. For this reason, in the list of objects proposed for the NASE 2024 challenge within the UNESCO-IDL project, a few more objects have been added, and the program is called the "Messier Challenge."

Fig 1: a) Charles Messier (left); b) Messier Catalog selected page, a list of 110 astronomical objects, published between 1774 and 1781 (right) (Credit: Wikicommons)

The NASE project proposed observing at least one of the selected objects (see Table 1), making a drawing or taking a photograph of it, and accompanying it with a brief story, either real or invented, related to the object. The observation could be made with the naked eye, binoculars, or a telescope if available: these options were related to the visibility of the selected objects for the activity, as, in addition to those distinguishable without instruments, other fainter objects were included.

Participants sent their report to NASE, indicating the names of the teacher and students, along with a brief description of the observed object and a drawing or photo of it. Some more advanced groups submitted objects from the Messier catalog not detailed in the list provided by NASE.

Table 1: Proposed Celestial Objects for the Messier Challenge

Name	ID Messier	Description	Mag.	Location	Image
Pleyades	M45	Open cluster	1,4	Taurus	
Hyades		Open cluster	0,5	Taurus	
Andomeda Galaxy	M31	Galaxy	3,5	Andromeda	
Orion Nebula	M42	Nebula	4,0	Orion	
Custer of Ptolomeo	M7	Open cluster	3,5	Scorpius	
Omega Centauri		Globular cluster	3,9	Centaurus	
Kappa Crucis/The Jewel Box		Open cluster	4,2	Crux	
Large Magellanic Cloud		Galaxy	0,7	Doradus/ Mensa	
Small Magellanic Cloud		Galaxy	2,9	Tucan	

3. The Observation

The proposal allowed not only for the appreciation of the night sky but also for the application of some of the content from the training sessions that NASE conducts worldwide, aimed at properly preparing a nighttime astronomical activity [5], such as:

1. **Choosing the location:** To avoid "light pollution," one should observe in a place far from roads and towns. It's also important to avoid being near streetlights or isolated lights.
2. **Choosing a date:** The best days are during the new moon or the waning phase, because early in the evening (when we will be observing), the moon has not yet risen.
3. **Choosing the right "work" clothing:** Even in summer, temperatures always drop at dusk, and wind often picks up (we'll be still for several hours).
4. **Using maps and adapting the eyes:** To find the chosen celestial object, it's helpful to use a sky map or planisphere. It's advisable to have a red flashlight, which doesn't dazzle like regular white flashlights (in the dark, the pupil gradually opens, and we can see faint objects better; when looking at something bright or a white light, the pupil contracts suddenly, deactivating the photoreceptor in the retina responsible for night vision, making it difficult to observe for a while).
5. **Tips for successful observation with the help of a cellphone:** Many apps can tell us what we are seeing by pointing the cellphone at the sky (Stellarium, Sky Map View, SkyView Lite, etc.), and they can be useful for locating the objects in the catalog.
6. **Observation with binoculars:** Although binoculars only offer a slight magnification, they gather much more light than our pupils and allow us to see faint objects that are almost invisible to the naked eye. They also enhance the color differences of objects. The recommended type for observation is 7x50 (magnifies the image 7 times, and the aperture of the front lens is 50mm). With higher magnifications, the image moves a lot, making them difficult to use. For this reason, it's recommended to mount them on a tripod to avoid the vibrations transmitted by our hands, which make observation harder, or to use a chair or wall to support the binoculars.
7. **Selecting objects of interest in each case:** For example, the Pleiades or the Hyades are easily detectable with the naked eye and are interesting objects to observe with binoculars. Other objects like the Andromeda Galaxy (M31), the Orion Nebula (M42), Omega Centauri, as well as the two Magellanic Clouds and the Milky Way in general,

and clusters like Kappa Crucis or the Ptolemy Cluster, are better observed with a telescope.

Fig. 2 Map Messier Catalog complete, as the used for the Marathon

Although it was not NASE's intention to organize the so-called Messier Marathon [6] [7], the topic was addressed, as it is an astronomical event celebrated since the mid-1980s with the goal of observing as many objects from the Messier catalog as possible in a single night (without electronic search devices), following the distribution of objects across the celestial sphere (Fig. 2) and their sequential appearance throughout the night. These Messier marathons were first held in the USA and Spain. They are typically organized on the weekend closest to the New Moon of the March equinox (March 21) to ensure a dark sky night without the Moon. For example, in 2024, the New Moon occurred on March 10, so the marathon was scheduled for Saturday, March 9.

4. Messier Challenge: development

The Messier Challenge was carried out with great success. A total of 560 submissions were received from Africa (4), America (24), Asia (445), and Europe (86), from 13 different countries: Germany, Argentina, Armenia, Bulgaria, China, Spain, Iran, Lithuania, Nicaragua, Panama, Romania, Sweden, and Togo, many of which were created and developed collectively.

The selected locations were diverse, some within schools, while others invited participants to travel to areas far from the cities. Some educational institutions provided astronomical

instruments, such as binoculars, to their students so they could use them for one or two nights at home with their families. This dynamic made it difficult to estimate the number of people involved in the activity; we estimate that thousands of teachers, students, and their families across four continents took part in the challenge.

Between the equinoxes, NASE trainers collaborated intensively to promote the activity, share methods for better observation of the selected celestial objects, provide materials, and hold conferences and workshops (both in-person and virtual) in various countries, cities, and for very diverse audiences (Fig. 3).

Fig 3. Teachers conducting workshops and participating in preparatory video conferences.

Fig 4 Auger Observ. Station - Andromeda (left); Camping Municipal Station– Orion (right)

In a true starry celebration under the open sky, the community of Malargüe embraced the proposal as their own. The local municipal government provided spaces for workshops, videoconferences, and special meetings, and actively supported local institutions that participated not only throughout the year but even more so during the closing week, when the event combined the annular solar eclipse visible in Argentina (partially visible in Malargüe) on October 2, 2024 [8], and the Star Festival in the city, during a full day on Friday, October 4, 2024. Figures 4, 5, and 6 show the setup of the "celestial stations" for the Messier Challenge in Malargüe. Each station was dedicated to a specific object, and visitors, including city residents and tourists, toured all of them using a special "passport."

Fig. 5 Plaza San Martín Station, Rufino Ortega School

Fig 6. Manuel Savio Scool Station, Malargüe

The day ended with performances of theater, dance, music, and the presentation of awards and certificates to the participants, as well as speeches from the teachers who worked throughout the year (Fig. 7). **An event that will be hard to forget for those who were part of it.**

Fig 7. Planetario Malargüe: closing ceremony (left); The Pleyads, performance for the Messier Challenge (right)

On Saturday, October 5, the traditional closing videoconference (NASE+ Seminar) was held; the work submitted by children, young people, and adults from formal and non-formal educational institutions around the world was shared through presentations by NASE representatives in each country.

This closing event was held for the first time in the Argentine Republic, in the department of Malargüe, Mendoza, home to the Pierre Auger Observatory, the largest (3000 km² in area) and unique in the world (due to its multiple detection systems) for the study of cosmic rays with the highest energies.

The Departmental Mayor opened the meeting at the Municipal Planetarium, expressing gratitude to the international participants and promising to continue proposing Malargüe as a venue for the "Bridges between Cultures" meetings.

During the meeting, the representatives of different countries presented their achievements along with their students (the full presentations can be viewed on the NASE YouTube channel):

- China, with Professor Zhu Geya and her students. This professor led the teachers and students of the Zhongguancun Second Primary School within the Xingyun Astronomy Club. They organized several night outings with all of them and a television program with an audience of 10,000 viewers (Fig. 8).

Fig 8. Chine presentation during the online session and diffenet views of night observations (Credit: Zhu Geya).

children's imagination and discussions

Fig 9. Online presentations from the primary school students on the left and the director of the Byurakan Observatory on the right (Credit: Lilit Hovhannisyan and Areg Mickaelian, respectively).

- Iran, with Maryam Papari, director of the Mehr Observatory in Bushehr, along with various students and their work during the online meeting (Fig. 10, left) and a group photo of the Messier Challenge coordinators in Iran (Fig. 10, right).

Fig 10. Online presentation from Iran by the Director of the Mehr Observatory (left) and Group photo of Messier Challenge in Iran organizers (right) (Credit: Maryam Papari)

- Lithuania was represented in the online final session by a 14-year-old student, Rytis Babianskas (Fig. 11, left), who works by observing through robotic telescopes from his hometown in Kaunas. We also presented an image of the Messier objects he photographed (Fig. 11, right).

Fig 11. Presentation from Lithuania: telescope used in the challenge (left); image of one of the Messier Objects not listed in Table 1 (right) (Credit: Rytis Babianskas).

4.1 Submissions received: a selection

The submissions received were diverse: drawings, paintings, photographs, group activities, specific research, special reports on Messier objects, night observations, star parties, among others. We share some of them in Figures 12 to 16.

Fig. 12: Drawing of the Pleiades made by a 5-year-old student in Panama (left) (Credit: Madelaine Rojas); team working on observations at the National Autonomous University of Nicaragua (right) (Credit: Ligia Áreas).

Fig. 13 Andromeda Galaxy, art work by a 7 years old student in Sweden, Thor Lagerfärd (left). Following a line in Bulgaria for observing diffuse objects (right) (Credit: Ivo Jokin)

Fig. 14 Crab Nebula from Togo (left) (Credit: Doh Koffi Addor); Observing with a small telescope in Romania (right) (Credit: Corina Toma).

Fig. 15 The Pleyades by students of 5 and 4 years, from the small municipality of Espinosa de los Monteros in Spain (Credit: Bárbara de Aymerich)

Fig. 16 Learning to use small telescopes to observe Messier objects and researching them at the Rural School Río Colorado 8-659, in Pata Mora, southern Malargüe, Mendoza (Credit: Erme Oviedo).

As final product of a year of research and observation, the Nase Genral Catalog for Schools without Telescopes [9] was prepare. This catalog will be part of the regular materials in NASE courses.

5. Conclusions

As every year since 2018, Bridges Between Cultures is a very successful event that brings together people from all over the planet to celebrate the International Day of Light with a citizen science activity, each year different and always challenging.

In 2024, the invitation for the inhabitants of the planet is to look back at the night sky. We know that observation at night is not easy in schools, but it is an opportunity to involve families.

The legacy of Charles Messier, the Messier Catalog, allowed for thinking about different ways to organize astronomical data, and among the data, images, which were not always recorded on plates: some of the old images are drawings. The possibility of proposing a NASE General Catalog today, to include it as special material within the NASE Courses, was a cooperative and joint effort with a great result.

This year, the closing ceremony of Bridges Between Cultures and the NASE+ Seminar, in Argentina, and specifically in the city of Malargüe, where the largest cosmic ray observatory in the world is located, was a great opportunity to link traditional astronomy with astroparticle physics.

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Basic Concepts of Photographing Messier Objects

Sakari Ekko

Puolala School and Finnish Astronomical Society Ursa r.y., Turku,
Finland

Abstract

In this article I explain the basics of photographing Messier objects using an ordinary digital single lens reflex or system camera. The suitable camera, lenses and other equipment are described, as well as camera settings and how to find the objects in the sky. Processing the images is touched briefly, and some examples of using the photos in your lessons are given, too.

Foreword

Photographing Messier objects differ from taking ordinary snapshots in many ways:

1. Messier objects are often dim and small. They require long exposures at high ISO values and large aperture lenses with longer than normal focal length. The photographer has to compromise between these variables and properties of his/her camera.
2. The ground under the tripod feet is not stable; Earth rotates.

3. Most of the objects are difficult to find with a camera.
4. Dark skies without severe light pollution can be long away from your backyard.

In the following I will tell about the technique of Deep sky (DS) photography with ordinary equipment and how to use in your lessons DS photos taken by you or your students.

Fig. 1 Some Messier Objects

The camera

Modern mobile phone cameras work wonders, but they are not best suited for DS photography. A digital single lens reflex (DSLR) camera, system camera or good “bridge“ camera do better job here. It is important, that the noise level of the camera is low at high ISO

values, so that the **signal/noise (S/N) ratio** is high enough to separate the object from the background noise. A rule of thumb: the bigger the sensor, the bigger the pixels (the light-sensitive units in the sensor) and the more they collect photons and thus the S/N ratio is better, i.e. you can use a higher ISO value and still get a decent picture. But the bigger the sensor, the more expensive and bulky the camera and lenses are. An APS-C or MFT-sensor, both widely used in amateur DSLR- or system cameras, is a good compromise. The technique marches on all the time, and new cameras often have better S/N properties than older models.

The camera must have **manual settings** for exposure, f-stop, ISO and focusing. Most, if not all cameras in our category have these facilities. **A live view**, the possibility so see the view in camera monitor or electric viewfinder is very useful in finding correct focus. System and bridge cameras always show the live view, a DSLR needs a special function for it.

A **tilting monitor** saves your neck, when the camera points high in the sky.

The **crop factor** is the length of the diagonal of full-frame (24 x 36 mm) camera sensor divided by the corresponding measure in the actual camera sensor. Crop factor for an APS-C sensor is 1.5 (Canon 1.6), for a MFT sensor 2 and for 1" sensor 2.7. **Effective focal length (f_{eff})** is real focal length multiplied by the crop factor.

Fig. 2 Barndoor Mount

The lens

The important parameters of a lens are **aperture** and **focal length**. The first determines how much light the lens can gather, the latter the size of image of an object on the sensor. Common series for aperture numbers is 1, 1.4, 2, 2.8, 4, 5.6, etc., marked f:1, f:1.4 etc., where f is the focal length. The exposure time needed for the same effect on sensor is doubled for

every step right, and halved for every step left. For example, if you have a f:2.8 lens and expose 10 seconds, you will get the same effect at f:2 and 5 seconds or at f:1.4 and 2.5 seconds. Ergo: the smaller the aperture number, the better the lens is suited for DS photography. f:2.8 – f:1.4 lenses are good for our purposes.

The size of the image on the sensor is:

$$s = (a \times f) / 57.3$$

where s = the size of the image, a = the object's angular size in degrees and f = focal length in same units as s. Do not use the crop factor here!

An example: The angular size of M 42 is 1.5° x 1°. You use a 100 mm lens. The bigger dimension gives an image of $s = (1.5 \times 100 \text{ mm}) / 57.3 = 2.6 \text{ mm}$ broad image on the sensor. Note: a 57.3 mm focal length lens gives the scale 1 mm / degree.

M 42 is one of the biggest Messier objects. If you photograph the Ring Nebula M 27 (diameter = 76') with the same lens, you will get 0.036 mm diameter ring on the sensor. This is about 10 pixels wide and it can be difficult if not impossible to see M27 as a ring.

Which lens?

Always choose the **fastest lens** you have/can afford: An f:1.4 lens is faster than one with a bigger f-number.

For smaller objects you need a longer lens – but the longer the lens, the shorter the exposure time possible without elongated star images (trailing) due to the revolving of Earth. A starting point is the formula:

$$(500 \text{ s} / (f_{\text{eff}})) / \cos d$$

where d = object's declination. You find that you can use longer exposure time on objects north (or south) of the equator.

For example, if you have a 100 mm lens in an APS-C camera and the object is M 31 (d = 41°) you can expose $(500 \text{ s} / (100 \times 1.5)) / \cos 41^\circ = 4.4 \text{ s}$ without too much trailing. “Too much” is a matter of taste; you can try longer or shorter exposures and choose the one you find good enough for your purpose. For longer exposures you will need some kind of tracker to turn your camera against the turning of Earth.

In practice, a short tele lens of 85 – 200 mm effective focal length and aperture f:1.4 – 2.8 is a good choice. If you do not own a suitable lens, you can find a manual focus second hand lens for your camera at moderate price – almost nobody wants such a lens nowadays, but for this

purpose they are OK. The analogue era lenses are not as sharp wide open as modern versions for digital cameras, though. Stopping down a step (from f:1.4 to f:2, for example) can help, but you have to use a longer exposure time or higher ISO number.

Miscellaneous equipment

In DS photography, long exposures are necessary, and you need a **tripod**. DS objects are difficult to find by trying to point the camera to them, so adding a telescopic or red dot **finder** is a good idea. You will find my way to attach a finder in camera's flash shoe in (5).

A **head lamp with red light** is good to have in darkness. Red light does not blind you; you save your dark vision.

If you need **reading glasses**, take them with you. You have to look closely at the camera monitor.

Warm clothing is essential, because you will not move much.

A **star chart** with Messier objects marked.

Get familiar with your equipment

It is said that we lose 50 points of our IQ in darkness. I do not know of you, but I would not have much left after losing those 50 points, so I have to set my camera ready and rehearse before I go into the night.

You have to find in the camera manual (about 300 pages, but you do not have to read all of them) how to set:

- manual exposure
- manual aperture
- manual focusing
- manual white balance (WB)
- manual ISO setting
- 2 s self-timer
- live view and how to magnify it to help focusing
- JPG + RAW setting. RAW files make extensive corrections possible.
- noise reduction (NR)

In my experience as a sky photography tutor, finding and using camera's manual settings is maybe the most difficult part in this auto everything era, but most of the auto functions simply do not work in DS photography. Some cameras can have a night sky program; try it to see how it works for DS photography. It is possible that it has been designed for night-scape photography only.

Select the **longest practical exposure time** by the above formula, the **smallest f-number** (lens wide open) and try first, say, ISO 1600 and WB 4500 K, the latter to avoid the muddy brown sky colour caused by waste light. You can vary the settings after seeing your first images.

Make sure your **battery is fully charged** and if you have a spare, take that, too.

Screw the camera temporarily on the tripod to see that every small screw and the possible quick release plate is with you. Make a trial exposure with the room lights off to check that everything works.

Write a list of the equipment and camera settings on a card and have it in your camera bag for future use.

It is a good idea to select the night's object(s) before leaving for your chosen site. This, too, is easier in a warm and well-lit room. You can plan how to find your object with help of familiar asterisms and star-hop (follow a course of stars) to it.

DO YOUR HOMEWORK! When in darkness, it is too late to read the manual or try to find right settings.

The location

Finding a good location for DS photography is not easy in these days of ever-growing light pollution. You will find sky darkness maps in internet (4), but remember to check the intended location in advance for accessibility and place to erect your tripod and peace to take photographs – and that you are not on someone's private ground. Do not drive hundreds of kilometres for your first experiments; for training a not-so-ideal location near your house will do.

The “easy” Messier object

The great Andromeda Galaxy (M31), Pleiades (M45) and the Great Orion nebula (M42) are easy targets, discerned in almost any photo of the proper sky area. Begin with them, and you will get decent results after some training. Other bright open and globular clusters like M 36 – 38, M44, M13 and M4 are good targets, too.

Do not misunderstand the magnitudes in the Messier catalogue. They are total magnitudes, summing up the total brightness of extended objects. For example, the Dumbbell Nebula (M27) has magnitude 7.3 (1), but the light is almost evenly spread over its 8'.0 x 5.7' area.

The **surface brightness** is quite low, and it is not as easy to get in a photo as the magnitude suggests. In the case of a galaxy, you can find that the dimmer outer spiral arms are not seen in the image, only the bright central part. Do not expect to see fine details in your photos. Your camera is not the Hubble telescope, but you have made those photographs with your simple equipment, using your skills. That is satisfying.

In the field

Find a bright star, point your camera to it and, using the live view, magnify the star image as much as possible to focus on it. This is important, the stars are unforgiving for focus error. Find your object and frame it in the viewfinder or monitor using a finder or simply point the camera in the right direction (possible, but often difficult – you can't point it as easily as a rifle). Do not touch the focus! You can tape the focus ring, so that it will not move accidentally. Note: this trick does not work with motor-focusing lenses.

Shut off your red headlight, and you are ready to push the trigger. You remembered to set the 2 s delay before leaving? If not, your picture will inevitably be blurred. A “hat trick” will help, too: cover the lens with a hat or black cardboard sheet, open the shutter and wait some seconds, then uncover the lens, count seconds (one elephant, two elephants etc.), then cover the lens again and before the shutter shuts.

One of the benefits of digital photography is that you can immediately look at your picture in the monitor. Is it somewhat well exposed? Can you see your target in the picture? This can be difficult, because the target is often dim, small or star-like. Enlarge the image. Is it sharp? Stars trailing too much? If everything is OK, go on making different exposures or change the ISO-number; if not, correct your mistakes first.

Take a lot of photos, digital imaging costs nothing (if you forget the heaps of money you have spent on your equipment...). You can select the best shot at your computer later. A trick: the camera monitor will blind you in darkness, and you lose your dark vision. Keep one eye shut, and it will not be blinded.

Remember to take photos with a wider (shorter focal length) lens too. This will help locating the objects in the sky, and the photo will be good to have in your lessons.

It is easy to drop or forget something when working in darkness, so look closely through your working area and camera bag before leaving for home.

At the computer

Probably your images need processing. Any processing software can do basic corrections: lighten or darken the image, adjust the contrast etc., but a RAW converter can do a lot more. Adobe Photoshop Elements has a simple RAW converter, too. A lot is written on image processing, but learning by doing is a good way to proceed. You see the result of your action immediately and go back if needed.

How to use your DS images in your lessons

The internet is full of splendid DS images, so what is the worth of the modest pictures you or your students have made?

In high school, my students photographed the sky as an optional part of their astronomy studies. Once three students photographed the Orion area and made a big poster of their photo, with several stars and DS objects named. They were very proud of it, and sure they got to know that part of the sky and many of its DS objects. Photographing the sky is a very effective way to learn it and get familiar with its wonders. Back in a warm room you can rehearse what you have seen and find objects in your photos you have not seen in the field. Learning is doing, doing is learning. As a bonus is the satisfaction of the DIY project.

If you got hooked

ou will soon find, that to get better results you will need tracking. A wonderfully simple solution to track the sky for some minutes is a **barn door tracker (or Haig mount)**. It is easy to make in a school workshop and could be a project in itself. Fig ... shows the simplest form of barn door tracker. In the internet you can find different variations of it, some very complicated, but even the basic type is capable of decent results. I began my DS photography with self-made barn door tracker.

If you have a friend with a telescope on a tracking mount, you can **piggyback** your camera on the telescope.

Another option is **stacking**: make several short exposures without tracking and stack them in a stacking program like **Sequator** or **Deep Sky Stacker**. If you like to work with your computer (and your computer is capable of running a stacking program), stacking is a good way to get good results without a tracking mount.

Happy moments under the starry sky!

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(In Finnish, but the photos will tell how to attach a finder in camera’s hot shoe).

You will find several articles on barn door tracker/Haig mount by googling them in internet, as well as stacking programs.

The Messier catalog, legacy of the “comet Ferret”

Frédéric Pitout

Midi-Pyrénées Observatory, University of Toulouse, France

Abstract

Charles Messier is a French astronomer known for his famous catalog, which currently includes 110 diffuse celestial objects. Less well known is his previous career, which led him to become world famous for the list of nebulae, clusters and galaxies that not only bear his name, but still bear the identification he gave them more than 100 years ago. In this work, part of his life as a “comet hunter” serves not only to define the profile of a unique astronomer, but also as a recognition of his legacy.

The life and work of Charles Messier: A french astronomer and his catalog

Charles Messier, born in 1730 in Eastern France, is a name familiar to anyone with an interest in astronomy. His catalog of deep-sky objects, which includes galaxies, nebulae, and star clusters, remains one of the most significant achievements in the history of the field. But how did Messier come to make such a lasting contribution to astronomy?

Messier’s journey into the world of science was not a straightforward one. Initially, he trained to become an accountant, though the exact reason for his shift toward astronomy remains unclear. There is no definitive documentation explaining why Messier abandoned accounting for the stars, but it is likely that his passion for the subject played a role.

Fig. 1: Cluny Observatory

At the age of 20, Messier moved to Paris, where he began his career in astronomy. He was appointed assistant to the prominent French astronomer Joseph-Nicolas Delisle. From 1758 onward, Messier worked at the small Cluny Observatory in Paris – a modest facility that Delisle had built at the top of the Cluny mansion’s hexagonal tower, which was distinct from the larger and more famous Paris Observatory. Despite its size, the Cluny Observatory (fig. 1) was where Messier honed his skills and began his work cataloging celestial objects.

In 1771, following his marriage, Messier and his wife moved into the Cluny Observatory. This observatory would remain his residence until his death in 1817. In addition to his work as an astronomer, Messier was appointed Royal Navy astronomer, a position that was somewhat surprising given his primarily civilian background. His role in the Navy did not distract him from his research, however, and it was during this period that he compiled the famous Messier Catalog (fig. 2), which would go on to shape the field of astronomy for centuries to come.

Fig. 2: Catalog of nebulae and star clusters in the Proceedings of Royal Academy of Sciences in 1774.

Through his meticulous observations and cataloging, Messier provided an invaluable resource for astronomers, particularly in identifying objects that could be mistaken for comets. His catalog is still used by astronomers today as a reference point for deep-sky observations.

Charles Messier: a Comet Hunter who created a lasting astronomical legacy

Charles Messier is best known for his catalog of celestial objects, but his primary interest was in comets. This focus on comets is somewhat unusual, as Messier paid little attention to other astronomical phenomena. Over the course of his career, he studied more than 40 comets and is credited with discovering around 20. The most famous of these was given the nickname *Comet Ferret* by King Louis XV of France, a reference to the ferret, a small but curious animal known for its cleverness and tendency to "steal" objects. The ferret's reputation for hiding and collecting items reflects Messier's own meticulous nature in cataloging objects in the night sky.

Messier's dedication to his comet-hunting work led to his acceptance as a member of the Royal Academy of Sciences in Paris in 1778. He worked primarily from the Cluny Observatory, which, while now part of a medieval museum, once housed a modest and unique astronomical setup. The observatory's roof was made of wood and glass, with small windows that could be opened for observing the night sky. Although Messier's instruments were limited in quality—such as a small 15 mm aperture refractor telescope and a low-quality 150 mm reflector—these challenges did not hinder his passion for discovery. In fact, the relatively poor quality of his instruments may have made his cataloging of deep-sky objects more significant, as it allowed for easier observation of the Messier objects with more modern equipment.

Messier's first cataloged object was the Crab Nebula (M1), discovered in 1758 while he was searching for Halley's Comet. Although the Crab Nebula had been discovered earlier in 1731 by English astronomer John Bevis, Messier's catalog focused on objects that could be mistaken for comets, making it a valuable tool for astronomers of the time. His catalog was not limited to his own discoveries, and many of the objects were first identified by other astronomers, including his contemporaries. The initial Messier catalog, published in 1774, contained 45 objects, and over time, it was expanded to include 103 objects by 1781.

Messier's catalog was updated in later years, with an additional 23 objects included in 1783. After his death, further objects were added, and today the catalog is widely recognized as containing 110 objects. These objects include a variety of celestial phenomena, from galaxies to nebulae and star clusters. While Messier himself discovered 29 of these objects, many were identified by his colleagues, such as Pierre Méchain, who worked closely with him. Messier's catalog remains an essential resource for astronomers, providing a detailed and lasting record of the deep-sky objects that continue to be observed today.

In summary, Charles Messier's work is a testament to his dedication to astronomy, his meticulous nature, and his unique focus on cataloging celestial objects that could be mistaken for comets. Despite working with modest instruments, Messier created a catalog that remains a cornerstone of astronomical research.

The diversity of Messier Objects and their observability

The Messier catalog is a fascinating collection of diverse celestial objects, spanning various categories that showcase the richness of the universe. Among the objects listed are supernova remnants, such as M1 (the Crab Nebula, fig. 3), star clusters, both open and globular, H II regions like the Orion Nebula, galaxies, and planetary nebulae. Additionally, there are a few peculiar objects that may leave observers wondering about their inclusion, such as optical double stars—one of which is located in the Big Dipper constellation. This diversity of objects makes the Messier catalog not only scientifically valuable but also a delight for amateur astronomers.

Fig. 3. The Crab Nebula - Messier 1

One of the significant advantages of Messier's catalog is that many of the objects it contains can be observed with relatively small instruments, including binoculars and small telescopes. In fact, some objects, such as the Andromeda Galaxy (M31, fig 4), are visible to the nakedeye under dark skies. This accessibility is part of what makes the Messier objects so appealing to amateur astronomers.

Fig. 4 Andromeda Galaxy - Messier 31

For those looking to observe the Messier objects, there is good news: a significant number of these objects can be viewed on a single night, especially between mid-March and mid-April. The optimal latitude for observing all or most of the Messier objects in one night is approximately 25 degrees north. Interestingly, Charles Messier himself lived at a latitude of around 45-46 degrees north, which means that his observations likely involved more limited views of the full catalog in a single night. However, for observers situated closer to the ideal latitude, this provides an excellent opportunity to see a wide variety of Messier objects in one observing session.

In conclusion, the Messier catalog offers a remarkable variety of celestial objects that are both accessible to amateur astronomers and rich in scientific value. Whether using small instruments or the naked eye, observers around the world can enjoy the beauty and diversity of the Messier objects, making it a perfect starting point for those interested in exploring the wonders of the night sky.

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Some Lower Latitude Messier Objects and Some Nearby Stars

Hichem Guergouri¹, Jamal Mimouni²

1. CERIST, Technopole, Univ. of Constantine³, Constantine , Algeria

2. CERIST, Technopole and LPMPS, Depart. of Physics, Univ. of
Constantine

Abstract

This paper highlights the intersection of cultural heritage and modern astronomy through the study of Messier objects and their associated nearby stars, particularly those visible at middle and lower latitudes. It explores the historical contributions of Islamo-Arabic astronomy, emphasizing the legacy of Abd al-Rahman al-Sufi and the cultural significance of constellations such as Orion, Taurus, and Scorpius. The Messier objects have both historical and scientific importance, serving as tools for understanding star formation, galaxy evolution, and the structure of the cosmos. This work bridges ancient traditions and modern discoveries, celebrating humanity's shared exploration of the universe.

1. Bridging Cultures in Astronomy: The Legacy of Islamo-Arabic Contributions

The history of astronomy is rich with contributions from various cultures. The Chinese, Babylonians, Romans, and Incas have laid the foundations of early astronomy. These civilizations significantly enhanced astronomical knowledge, leaving a lasting impact on the

field. One of the most influential has been from Arabic and Islamic scholars. This talk aims to highlight the intersection of cultural heritage and modern astronomical understanding, particularly by focusing on nearby stars and nebulae associated with the Messier objects typically observed at middle latitudes, lower than those seen in most of Europe. In doing so, we will explore three emblematic celestial objects: the Orion Nebula, the Scorpion, and Taurus. However, before delving on these aspects, let us mention some scientific aspects related to the Messier objects [1].

1.1 Messier Objects: their Role in Modern Astronomy

These objects continue to provide insights, not just for their historical significance, but also for their ongoing role in research into areas like star formation, stellar evolution, and galaxy formation. These objects serve as laboratories for studying star formation, stellar evolution, galaxy formation [2], and even the mysterious phenomena associated with dark matter and supermassive black holes. It goes without saying that their prominence, and for some of them, their relative closeness and thus prone to the selection effect is no stranger in this regard. For example, the Orion Nebula (M42) continues to be a focal point for the study of how stars and planetary systems form, particularly with the new insights provided by the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST), which is able to peer into the dense gas clouds where young stars are born. Messier objects like M31 (Andromeda Galaxy) also provide valuable information about the structure and dynamics of galaxies, offering clues to how galaxies merge and evolve over cosmic timescales.

Incluso en cosmología, los objetos Messier desempeñan un papel importante, ya que mejoran nuestra comprensión de la expansión del universo, la materia oscura y los agujeros negros supermasivos. También ayudan a calibrar la escala de distancias cósmicas, crucial para determinar el tamaño y la edad del universo, y proporcionan una visión del pasado y una guía para su evolución. Dicho esto, la investigación sobre la materia oscura y los agujeros negros supermasivos se basa principalmente en estudios de galaxias a gran escala.

1.2 A legacy from the Golden age of the Arabo-Islamic civilization

A significant part of this discussion revolves around the names of bright stars near Messier objects, many of which have Arabic origins. As the historical records attest, Arabic culture has had a profound impact on the development of astronomy [3], with the names of most of the brightest stars in the sky having been derived from Arabic. The Arabic-speaking cultures, along with the contributions of the Chinese, Babylonians, Romans, and others, laid the

foundation for early astronomy. These civilizations helped advance our understanding of the stars, many of which continue to bear Arabic names in modern astronomical catalogs—names such as Regulus, Saiph, and Andromeda. Needless to say, the Arabo-Islamic civilization has also to its records more substantial contributions such as the development of observational instruments, mathematical models, and systematic catalogs that are not delves with here.

Fig. 1 The Book of Fixed Stars by Abd al-Rahman al-Sufi

One of the most renowned figures in early Islamic astronomy is Abd al-Rahman al-Sufi, a Persian astronomer who wrote extensively in Arabic [4]. His work, “The Book of Fixed Stars”[5] (*fig. 1*), meticulously documented 48 known constellations, presenting them with remarkable accuracy—so much so that his observations still hold up by modern standards. Al-Sufi’s contributions to star cataloging were invaluable, and his work provided a bridge between ancient and modern astronomy.

Perhaps his most significant discovery was the first documented mention of what we now know as the Andromeda Galaxy. Al-Sufi noted the existence of this "spot" in the sky long before it was recognized as a galaxy. In recognition of his contributions, some astronomers, and notably the Arab Union for Astronomy and Space Sciences, have proposed renaming the Andromeda galaxy as the "Al-Sufi" galaxy.

2. The Role of Equatorial and Galactic Planes in Observing Messier Objects

One of the key figures in early Islamic astronomy, *Abd al-Rahman al-Sufi*, made significant contributions by creating an incredibly precise catalog of stars and celestial objects. His work has had a lasting influence on modern astronomy, and his catalog is still celebrated for its accuracy. As we explore the Messier objects, we are reminded of the rich history of astronomy and the cultural bridges that connect us to the past.

When observing Messier objects, it is essential to consider the equatorial map, which provides a more accurate and pedagogically valuable tool for understanding the night sky. While many are familiar with the horizontal or circular maps commonly used in modern astronomy, the equatorial map offers a more practical way to locate celestial objects, particularly those visible from lower latitudes. This map divides the sky into a coordinate system based on the celestial equator, making it easier to find objects like the Messier catalog items.

An intriguing feature of the equatorial map is the intersection between the equatorial plane and the galactic plane. The galactic plane, which represents the plane of our Milky Way galaxy, intersects the equatorial plane in several key regions of the sky. When objects lie along this intersection, they are within a particularly rich region of the cosmos, surrounded by a dense collection of stars, nebulae, and other deep-sky objects. Indeed quite few of them lie along the Milky Way's disk. This is especially true for objects like those found in the Orion constellation, which is located near the intersection of these two planes and partly for Taurus.

Fig. 2 There is a pedagogical interest in using an equatorial map instead of the usual horizontal one: equatorial plane (Green), ecliptic plane (Blue), galactic band, and the points where they intersect with other.

For example, when observing constellations like Orion or Gemini, which are often visible from lower latitudes, astronomers are looking at a backdrop filled with the light of numerous stars and nebulae from the Milky Way. These regions offer a rich and visually stunning environment for stargazers, where the galactic and equatorial planes meet, revealing an extraordinary array of celestial objects. The relationship between these two planes makes the Messier objects even more captivating, as they are set against a background teeming with other astronomical wonders.

In conclusion, understanding the intersection of the equatorial and galactic planes not only enhances our ability to locate Messier objects but also highlights the richness of the cosmic landscape in which these objects exist. The equatorial map, with its pedagogical and practical uses, is an essential tool for both amateur and professional astronomers, offering a deeper appreciation for the night sky.

3. Exploring the stars: A journey through some Messier Objects and their cultural significance

The constellations and stars that adorn our night sky have inspired countless generations, and their stories transcend cultures and centuries. Among the many celestial wonders, the Orion, Taurus, and Scorpius constellations stand out not only for their prominence but also for their rich cultural significance, particularly in Arabic astronomy.

Fig. 3 Orion Constellation in the al-Sufi's masterpiece.

3.1 Orión: El Cazador y su rica mitología

Orion, known as *al-Jabbar* in Arabic, meaning "the giant" or "the strong man," is one of the most recognizable constellations in the sky. It is also called *al-Sayad*, meaning "the hunter," and *al-Jawza*, which can be translated as "the central one" or "the dual one," referring to its position in the sky [6].

Its star names, such as *Betelgeuse* (the armpit of Orion) and *Rigel* (the foot of Orion), provide a fascinating glimpse into the linguistic and cultural heritage of Arabic astronomy. In fact, the stars in Orion's belt are often associated with a belt or a central feature. *Alnitak* means "The girdle" or "the belt"), *Alnilam* meaning "The string of pearls". Finally *Mintaka* means "The region", while the nearby stars in the "sword" region add further to the symbolism of the constellation as a warrior or hunter.

The Orion constellation (Fig. 3) also contains several notable Messier objects (Fig. 4), most famously the Orion Nebula (M42), a stellar nursery where new stars are born. However, it is important to note that the nebula's appearance in photographs can be misleading. The vibrant colors seen in long-exposure photographs are not visible to the naked eye, and the nebula's light comes not directly from the gas and dust, but from the stars within and behind it. This makes the glossy pictures Orion Nebula a "fake" object in a sense, as its true nature is far more complex than what is visible from Earth. Indeed, photographs result from long-exposure imaging and false-color processing; this is why photos often appear different from what we might see with the naked eye. Yet the enormous amount of details from it is due to its proximity to us, which allows for these magnificently looking views when enhanced.

Fig. 4 Some beautiful nebulae in Orion

This renders the glossy images of the Orion Nebula somewhat 'deceptive,' as its true nature is far more complex than what is visible to the naked eye from Earth. These photographs result from long-exposure imaging and false-color processing, which explains why they differ significantly from what we could observe directly. However, it is proximity to us which allows for an extraordinary level of detail to be captured, when enhanced through advanced imaging techniques.

3.2 Taurus: the bull and its stars

The *Taurus* constellation (Fig. 5) known as *al-Thawr* in Arabic, is another prominent constellation in the sky, with its brightest star, *Aldebaran*, meaning "the eye of the bull" in Arabic. The name reflects the imagined image of the bull, with Aldebaran symbolizing the animal's eye. The constellation is also home to the Pleiades (*al-Thurayya* in Arabic), or the Seven Sisters, a beautiful open star cluster that holds both astronomical and cultural significance. In Arabic culture, the number of stars visible in the Pleiades cluster is often used as a test of visual acuity. Seeing six or seven stars in the cluster was considered an indication of sharp eyesight.

Fig. 5 Taurus Constellation from al-Sufi's "The Book of Fixed Stars"

Taurus also contains some intriguing Messier objects, such as M1, the Crab Nebula, which marks the remnants of a supernova explosion. This object, visible with a small telescope, adds to the richness of the Taurus constellation, making it a popular target for stargazers.

3.2 Scorpius: The Scorpion and its bright stars

The *Scorpius* constellation (Fig. 6), known as *Al-Aqrab* in Arabic, meaning "the scorpion," is another striking feature of the southern sky. One of its brightest stars, *Antares*, marks the heart of the scorpion, while another star, *Shaula*, located at the tail, gives the impression of a raised stinger. These names provide insight into the imaginative way Arabic astronomers viewed the stars, interpreting their positions and relationships in a vivid and meaningful way.

Fig. 6 Scorpius Constellation from al-Sufi’s “The Book of Fixed Stars”

Interestingly, Shaula (Lambda Scorpii) at the tail of Scorpius can’t be seen easily from latitudes above around 45°. At Algiers’s latitude (~37°), Shaula rises above the horizon by no more than 16° in summer. At other locations, one can easily calculate the rising angle at culmination of any object from the simple formula See the table at below for the latitudes for a number of Messier objects:

$$\text{Rising angle} = 90^\circ - (\text{latitude of the place}) + (\text{declination of the object})$$

In Figure 7, se presentan las latitudes de varios objetos Messier.

<p>1.M6 (Butterfly Cluster) 1. Common Name: Butterfly Cluster 2. Type: Open Cluster 3. Declination: -32.2533°</p> <p>2.M7 (Ptolemy's Cluster) 1. Common Name: Ptolemy's Cluster 2. Type: Open Cluster 3. Declination: -34.815°</p> <p>3.M8 (Lagoon Nebula) 1. Common Name: Lagoon Nebula 2. Type: Nebula with Open Cluster 3. Declination: -24.379444°</p> <p>4.M16 (Eagle Nebula) 1. Common Name: Eagle Nebula 2. Type: Star-forming Nebula with Open Cluster 3. Declination: -13.806667°</p> <p>5.M17 (Omega Nebula) 1. Common Name: Omega Nebula, Swan Nebula 2. Type: Emission Nebula 3. Declination: -16.171667°</p> <p>6.M18 1. Common Name: (No specific common name) 2. Type: Open Cluster 3. Declination: -17.813056°</p> <p>7.M19 1. Common Name: (No specific common name) 2. Type: Globular Cluster 3. Declination: -26.267778°</p> <p>8.M20 (Trifid Nebula) 1. Common Name: Trifid Nebula 2. Type: Emission Nebula and Reflection Nebula 3. Declination: -22.971111°</p>	<p>A list of the Messier objects visible from Northern Africa 35°, but not from Middle or Northern Europe</p> <p>... along with their celestial latitudes (declination), their common names and the type of astronomical objects</p>	<p>9. M22 9. Common Name: (No specific common name) 10. Type: Globular Cluster 11. Declination: -23.904722°</p> <p>10. M28 9. Common Name: (No specific common name) 10. Type: Globular Cluster 11. Declination: -24.869444°</p> <p>11. M54 9. Common Name: (No specific common name) 10. Type: Globular Cluster 11. Declination: -30.479444°</p> <p>12. M55 9. Common Name: (No specific common name) 10. Type: Globular Cluster 11. Declination: -30.964722°</p> <p>13. M69 9. Common Name: (No specific common name) 10. Type: Globular Cluster 11. Declination: -32.292222°</p> <p>14. M70 9. Common Name: (No specific common name) 10. Type: Globular Cluster 11. Declination: -32.2925°</p> <p>15. M75 9. Common Name: (No specific common name) 10. Type: Globular Cluster 11. Declination: -21.921111°</p> <p>These objects are predominantly located in the Southern sky, making them more visible from the Southern Hemisphere and tropical latitudes in the Northern Hemisphere, like that of Algeria.</p>
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Fig. 7 Objetos Messier visibles para el norte de África

Scorpius is also home to several Messier objects, including M4 and M80 (Fig. 8), two notable globular clusters. These dense collections of stars add to the allure of the constellation, which is already rich with both mythological and astronomical significance.

Fig. 8 Messier Objects in Scorpio: the globular clusters M4 y M80

4. Connecting Cultures Through Stars and Stories

The rich traditions of Arabic astronomy, especially the work of astronomers such as *Abd al-Rahman al-Sufi*, continue to influence modern stargazing. Al-Sufi's detailed catalog of stars, which includes the first known descriptions of the Andromeda galaxy, highlights the deep connections between ancient cultures and their understanding of the night sky. This should be put in parallel with Chinese, Indian, and European astronomical traditions.

In this context, the names and myths associated with stars are not just a reflection of the past but also a bridge connecting various cultures and their interpretations of the universe. The stories and names passed down through generations continue to inspire modern astronomers and stargazers, reminding us of the collective nature of humanity's exploration of the cosmos.

4.1 A gift from the Sahara

To end this journey through the stars, a special gift from the Sahara Desert in Algeria—an picture of the starry sky around Orion captured by renowned astrophotographer Mohammed Aissa Moussa—offers a glimpse into the pure beauty of the night sky (32°29'N), where the stars shine brightest in the absence of moonlight. The Sahara, with its pristine skies, serves as a reminder of the incredible clarity and magnificence of the universe when seen in its natural, unspoiled state.

In conclusion, whether through the bright stars of Orion, the rich symbolism of Taurus, or the striking presence of Scorpius, the Messier objects provide a window into the vastness of the cosmos. Through the lens of astronomy, cultures, and the enduring legacy of early astronomers, we continue to explore, discover, and marvel at the wonders of the universe.

Fig. 9 Sahara dessert, starry sky around Orion

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Abd al-Rahman al-Sufi: The Pioneer Astronomer and His Observation of the Andromeda Galaxy

Fateme Hasheminasab

Thaqib Astronomical Society, Bushehr, Iran

Abstract

Abd al-Rahman al-Sufi, also known as Azophi, was a renowned Persian astronomer whose contributions to the field of astronomy remain remarkable even centuries later. Born in 903 CE in the city of Rayy, near modern-day Tehran, Iran, he lived during the Islamic Golden Age, a time of great scientific and intellectual progress. Al-Sufi's meticulous observations and detailed records bridged the knowledge of ancient Greek astronomy and the rich astronomical traditions of the Islamic world.

Al-Sufi is best known for his seminal work, *The Book of Fixed Stars* (964 CE), which described the positions, brightness, and colors of stars. His integration of Greek, Arabic, and Persian astronomical traditions created a unique resource for generations of astronomers. Among his significant achievements was the first recorded observation of the Andromeda Galaxy, which he described as a "small cloud" in the constellation Andromeda. This groundbreaking discovery predates similar observations in Europe by several centuries, making al-Sufi a pioneer in identifying galaxies beyond the Milky Way.

The Legacy of Abd al-Rahman al-Sufi and His Observations of the Andromeda Galaxy

Abd al-Rahman al-Sufi (Fig. 1), also known as Azophi in the West, was a famous Persian astronomer who lived during the Islamic Golden Age. He was born in 903 CE, in Rayy, near modern-day Tehran, Iran. From a young age, al-Sufi was drawn to the study of the stars and mathematics, fields that flourished in the cultural and intellectual environment of the Islamic Golden Age.

Al-Sufi spent much of his life working under the patronage of the Buyid rulers, particularly Adud al-Dawla, in the Persian city of Shiraz. It was during this time that he produced his seminal work, *The Book of Fixed Stars*. His meticulous approach to observation and his commitment to accuracy reflected his deep passion for understanding the cosmos.

Fig 1. Abd al-Rahman al-Sufi

The “Book of Fixed Stars”

Al-Sufi’s most important book, *The Book of Fixed Stars*, was written in 964 CE. In this book, he described the 48 constellations recorded by the Greek astronomer Ptolemy and added his own observations. Al-Sufi corrected the positions and brightness of many stars and provided illustrations for each constellation. These illustrations were drawn as they appeared in the sky and on a celestial globe, helping people better understand the stars.

Observation of Andromeda Galaxy

One of al-Sufi's most amazing discoveries was his description of the Andromeda Galaxy, which he called a "small cloud." This was the first recorded observation of this galaxy, made long before telescopes were invented. The Andromeda Galaxy is about 2.5 million light-years away from Earth and is the closest large galaxy to our Milky Way.

Al-Sufi's drawing of the Andromeda Galaxy showed it as a faint, hazy patch in the night sky. This observation is significant because the galaxy is only barely visible to the naked eye under perfect conditions. Al-Sufi's ability to note and record this celestial object speaks to his remarkable observational skills and the advanced understanding of astronomy during his time.

The Andromeda Galaxy is now known as a massive spiral galaxy with several satellite galaxies. Modern telescopes have revealed its detailed structure, including its spiral arms, bright nucleus, and large star clusters. Al-Sufi's work (Fig. 2) laid the foundation for recognizing the existence of other galaxies outside the Milky Way, expanding humanity's view of the universe.

Fig 2. Oldest surviving depiction of the Andromeda (dots at the tip of the mouth of the lower) by Al-Sufi

Other contributions to Astronomy

Al-Sufi also studied the brightness and colors of stars and corrected errors in earlier star catalogs. For example, he noted the unchanged color of Sirius, the brightest star in the night sky.

In addition, Al-Sufi's cataloging of star magnitudes and their precise locations on celestial maps provided future astronomers with a reference point for identifying and tracking stars over time. His work was essential for preserving the astronomical knowledge of earlier civilizations and passing it on to future generations.

Legacy

Al-Sufi's work influenced both Islamic and European astronomy. His book was translated into Latin and used by many astronomers in the Middle Ages. Today, a crater on the Moon is named "Azophi" in his honor.

Conclusions

Abd al-Rahman al-Sufi's observations of the stars and galaxies show how advanced Islamic astronomy was in the 10th century. His description of the Andromeda Galaxy as a "small cloud" was a groundbreaking discovery. Al-Sufi's careful work and detailed illustrations have made him one of the most respected astronomers in history. His legacy continues to inspire people to explore the wonders of the universe.

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The Constellations and the “Uranometría Argentina”: a legacy for the world

Santiago Paolantonio

Museum of Córdoba Observatory, Argentina

Abstract

The first work of the Argentine National Observatory, based in the city of Córdoba, Argentina, was the *Uranometría Argentina*, a catalog and atlas of the stars visible to the naked eye in the southern sky. This work, completed in the 19th century, provided, for the first time, a uniform view of the entire sky, alongside those existing in the northern hemisphere. The high quality of the work was immediately recognized internationally and became a significant contribution to astronomical science. Several decades later, this work was used as a reference to define the boundaries of the 88 constellations that are recognized today

1. Introduction

On a clear and dark night, with no moon and far from any light pollution, more than three thousand stars can be counted in the sky with the naked eye. This nocturnal spectacle, which has captivated humanity since ancient times, led various civilizations to imagine figures by grouping stars or dark areas, which served as guides for exploring the celestial sphere and new lands. In China, dragons were seen; in the Middle East and Europe, deities, giants, and later a cross; in America, the footprints of ostriches (ñandú) and braziers. The brightest stars received names and were referenced to the imagined asterisms, the constellations, which divide the sky into sections just as nations do on Earth.

Even today, despite the fact that each star can be unambiguously located using its coordinates, astronomers maintain the tradition of referencing them to the constellation to which they "belong," often retaining the names given to them in ancient times.

The constellations recognized today primarily derive from the 48 listed by Ptolemy in the *Almagest*, as well as those introduced later by navigators and astronomers who observed the southern skies in recent centuries. Today, the celestial sphere is divided into 88 constellations, as established by the International Astronomical Union in 1930.

The process that led to the adoption of the names and boundaries of these asterisms was long and complex. It involved empires, institutions, and renowned astronomers, and in the end, the contribution made by the Argentine National Observatory in the *Uranometría Argentina* was decisive.

2. Brief history of the “Uranometría Argentina”

The main founding goal of the Argentine National Observatory was the creation of catalogs with precise positions of the southern stars obtained with a meridian circle, a telescope specialized in this type of work, and through photography.

However, due to the Franco-Prussian War that affected Europe during the formation of the Argentine observatory, the arrival of this key instrument for carrying out the work was delayed by several months. The construction of the institution's headquarters was also delayed, so the founding director, astronomer Benjamin A. Gould, together with the four first assistants hired, who were idle due to these circumstances, decided to create an "austral uranometry," similar to those existing in the northern hemisphere at the time.

As with any "uranometry," it would be a catalog and map of all the stars observed with the naked eye over the course of a year, in this case, the pristine sky of Córdoba at the time. The term uranometry has been used for this type of work since the early 17th century, when Johann Bayer [1] published an atlas of this kind. The name derives from Urania, the Greek muse of astronomy, and can be interpreted as "measurement of the heavens."

The first observation for the new austral uranometry was made on November 14, 1870. The assistants Williams Davis, Miles Rock, John M. Thome, and Clarence Hathaway initiated it from the terrace of their accommodations in the city of Córdoba. Later, when the headquarters were completed, others, such as Walter Davis and Albert K. Marsfield, contributed by drawing the star maps.

The director of the Observatory, who did not participate in the observations due to his severe myopia, focused on organizing the work, reviewing what had been done, and studying the results.

A great number of works by the most renowned astronomers were analyzed, from which a unification of star names and the boundaries of constellations was proposed, aiming to make changes with the least amount of modification possible in terms of the stars' associations and the names that had been accepted up until that time, in an effort to achieve the broadest possible acceptance among colleagues. As will be seen, this organization of stellar names and constellation boundaries was one of the most important contributions of this work, but not the only one.

The detailed investigation of the observations led to the discovery of around two hundred stars that changed in brightness over time, known as "variable stars," of great interest to the astronomers of the time—a significant number, considering that relatively few had been known up until that point, mostly from the northern hemisphere.

Additionally, the study of the distribution of stars led to the discovery of an unknown stellar system, now known as the "Gould Belt," which continues to be the subject of numerous studies.

The quality of the work done was a result of the ability of the observers, the studies carried out by the Director, and the detailed verifications performed to detect possible errors. In fact, while the observations were essentially completed by the time the Argentine National Observatory was inaugurated on October 24, 1871, due to the thoroughness applied, the work was only published in 1879 [2][3].

The new uranometry included for the first time stars up to magnitude 7, a total of 7,756, visible between the celestial south pole and declination 10° north. In this way, alongside the *Uranometria Nova* by the renowned German astronomer Friedrich Argelander, who was Dr. Gould's mentor, a uniform view of the entire sky was finally achieved. It was published in Volume 1 of the *Results of the Argentine National Observatory* in 1877 (Atlas) and 1879 (Catalog and History), the first work produced by this institution [4]. The *Uranometría Argentina* immediately received multiple recognitions, such as a gold medal awarded by the Royal Society in 1883.

The cover of this work, shown in the digitized image in Figure 1, is one of those preserved at the Astronomical Observatory of the National University of Córdoba, Argentina, the current name of the observatory.

While the catalog details the coordinates and brightness of each star included, the maps, unlike previous uranometries, were drawn to closely mimic what was observed, leaving aside the beautiful but useless (for scientific work) allegorical drawings of the constellations. Particular emphasis was placed on outlining the "Milky Way." In Figure 2, as an example, a detail of the area surrounding the "Cross" constellation is shown.

Fig 1. Covers of the atlas and catalog of the *Uranometría Argentina*. In the first one, a detailed drawing of the city of Córdoba as seen from the Observatory can be appreciated (OAC Library, digitized by S. Paolantonio).

Fig. 2 Detail of one of the maps from the *Uranometría Argentina*, area of the constellation of the Cross. (OAC Library, digitized by S. Paolantonio)

3. The Celestial Map: division of the sky into constellaciones

3.1 Anarchy

Before 1600, almost all stars were designated by their positions in asterisms or by alignments between them, a method that was ambiguous and imprecise. Combined with the fact that constellations changed in number and name over time, this led to a true chaos. In particular, the boundaries were not defined and varied according to each astronomer, who usually took great liberties in this regard.

This anarchic scenario began to change in the 17th century, particularly with the use of the telescope, thanks to the contributions of notable astronomers such as Johann Bayer [1], John F. W. Herschel [5], and Nicolas L. de Lacaille [6], among others. Despite this, by the mid-19th century, identification errors were still common, which was unsustainable in an era when astronomical instruments had reached remarkable advancements, stellar positions were being recorded by the tens of thousands, and astrophysical studies were beginning to develop rapidly.

3.2 Proposed order

At the end of the Great War, in 1919, astronomers from a group of countries created the International Astronomical Union, to which the majority of the world's nations gradually joined, becoming today the governing body of astronomical activity.

The first Assembly of the Union was held in 1922 in Rome, Italy, during which the exclusive use of Latin names for the constellations and their abbreviations with the three-letter system currently in use was established [7].

At the following meeting, held in 1925 in Cambridge, England, a motion was presented to address the pending issue of precisely defining the boundaries of the constellations, an important aspect for many works, such as meteor and bolide observation, the study of variable stars, and nova observation.

The Belgian astronomer Eugène J. Delporte of the Royal Observatory in Uccle was tasked with making a proposal for the demarcation, which would be presented for consideration at the next congress.

3.3 The solution

The immense work that Delporte had to undertake to bring order to the existing inaccuracies was largely alleviated thanks to the proposal made in the *Uranometría Argentina* (UA) [8][9].

To define the boundaries of the constellations, Delporte followed the proposal made in the UA, using arcs of right ascension circles and parallels of declination. The primary challenge was to select these boundaries in such a way that they did not differ too much from those used in the most important atlases of the time. He also adopted the equinox of 1875.0, coincidentally with the UA, despite the fact that by that time positions were already being given for 1900.0, clearly highlighting the importance given to this.

At the meeting held at Leiden University, Netherlands, in 1928, Delporte presented the proposal, which was accepted by the Assembly [10]. Two years later, the report was published under the name “*Délimitation scientifique des constellations*” [11], which included a table with the defined boundaries of 88 constellations and a set of maps where they were drawn. The maps were drawn in the same scale and projection used in the UA, although for economic reasons, they were published at a smaller size, only 40% of the original. In Figure 3, the area around the south pole is compared, showing the work published by the Córdoba Observatory (the UA) and Delporte's proposal. The similarity between the two is evident; meanwhile, in Figure 4, some modifications introduced in the boundaries of the constellations can be seen to respect the use of arcs of right ascension circles and parallels of declination.

Fig. 3. Map of the southern celestial pole taken from “*Délimitation scientifique des constellations*” (right), compared with the same area of the sky published in *Uranometría Argentina* (left)

Uranometria Argentina 1877

Delporte 1930

Fig. 4 Modifications introduced in the limits of the constellations of the Argentine Uranometria (above, map 3) and those resolved in Delporte 1930 (below, map 3S) (Credit: S. Paolantonio).

3. Conclusion

As stated, the influence of the work of the astronomers at the Argentine National Observatory, carried out at the end of the 19th century, aimed at creating a detailed map of the southern sky, following certain criteria that were not internationally adopted at the time, is evident.

This makes the *Uranometría Argentina* a pioneering work that is still internationally recognized today.

It is also important to note that the current boundaries of the constellations were largely based on the proposal made in this work, a choice that was not arbitrary but a result of its high quality.

This first work marked the beginning of others of great importance, such as the Great Catalogs, which include precise positions of thousands of southern stars, the “Córdoba Durchmusterung,” an atlas and catalog created following the standards of its predecessor, the Bonner Durchmusterung, and the participation in the international photographic project “Carte du Ciel,” among many others.

These contributions significantly advanced the progress of astronomy, particularly in our current understanding of the nearby universe, our galaxy, the Milky Way.

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NASE General Catalog for schools without Telescope

Rosa, M. Ros¹, Ricardo Moreno² and Beatriz García³

1. Politechnic University of Catalonia, Barcelona, Spain

2. Colegio Retamar, Madrid, Spain

3. CONICET, National Technological University, Mendoza, Argentina

Abstract

Since ancient times, astronomers have cataloged celestial objects. Initially, star lists were created, detailing celestial coordinates, magnitudes, and descriptions of their characteristics, and only included objects that could be detected with the naked eye. With the introduction of the telescope in astronomy in 1609, catalogs began to expand, incorporating faint and diffuse objects, and improving the data related to positions on the celestial sphere, brightness, temperatures, and other relevant information. Naming and cataloging objects, organizing and preserving data and information, is part of human nature. This contribution shares a "modern" experience in the creation of the catalog proposed by the community that forms the Network for Astronomy School Education.

Introduction

During the year 2024, NASE (Network of Astronomy School Education) [1] organized a project called the “Messier Challenge” in celebration of the International Day of Light (IDL-M16), an event held annually by UNESCO [2]. The main goal of this project was to promote sky observation among secondary and primary school students in all the countries where astronomy is promoted with the help of NASE. It is true that in many schools, students observe the sky by recognizing constellations and even the planets visible to the naked eye, but NASE aimed to go a step further, encouraging students to also discover the diffuse objects listed in some astronomical catalogs, which can be a source of interest to learn more about the various stages of stellar evolution. Since Charles Messier was one of the first to list such objects, his catalog [3], published in 1774, was used as the foundation for the project.

Additionally, NASE included several objects from the southern hemisphere that were easy to observe and not included in the mentioned catalog, which mainly focuses on the northern hemisphere skies.

For this reason, the objects visible to the naked eye or with binoculars from the "Messier Catalog" were selected, and some objects from the "New General Catalogue" (NGC) [4] were added.

The "NGC" is a well-known catalog, created in 1888 by John Louis Emil Dreyer, that contains 7,840 objects and is widely used in night sky observation; it is much more comprehensive than the "Messier Catalog," which includes only 110 objects.

The initially suggested list included the Pleiades, the Hyades, the Andromeda Galaxy, the Orion Nebula, the Ptolemy Cluster, Omega Centauri, the Jewel Box, the Large Magellanic Cloud, and the Small Magellanic Cloud.

The NASE proposal invited observers to explore any celestial object of interest, even if it wasn't on the initially suggested list, and to use whatever instrument they preferred. For example, a 14-year-old student from Lithuania submitted various observations made with a robotic telescope, from which they obtained excellent photographs (Fig. 1). The brightest stars were given names and referenced to imagined asterisms, the constellations, which divide the sky into parts just as nations do on Earth.

Fig. 1. M51 Whirlpool Galaxy (Credit: Rytis Babianskas)

The "Messier Challenge" project was a great success, receiving 560 reports from many of the countries where NASE conducts its teacher training courses in astronomy education each year. Since the project created a direct connection with hundreds of schools worldwide, a vote

was organized among the teachers and students involved to select the most popular and impactful objects—those that everyone would love to observe or find in their own catalog. Voting forms were distributed, and hundreds of responses were received, resulting in a list of objects proposed by participants to be included in a future NASE catalog.

The "challenge" was conducted in an open manner, welcoming all types of observations, and it is known that many educational institutions, astronomical associations, and local planetariums offered special observation sessions so that students could first observe and then draw or photograph the objects on the proposed list (Fig. 2 and 3).

Fig. 2: Observation with students in Iran (Credit: Sama Kordjazi and Mohammad Hassan Haji Hosseini).

Fig. 3: Drawing the Pleiades previously observed in Argentina.(Credit: Martina Aburto Milicevic)

In most cases, the observations were made with the naked eye or, at most, using binoculars mounted on a tripod. For this reason, the "winners" of the vote were objects visible without a telescope.

Let us now take a look at the result of the project, which we have compiled under a title that seems suggestive to us astronomers at NASE (as it recalls the well-known NGC). We present here the "NASE GENERAL CATALOG (NGC) for schools without telescope".

NASE General Catalog-NGC for schools without telescope

The catalog includes 16 diffuse objects: 4 nebulae, 4 galaxies, 4 open star clusters, and 4 globular clusters. Some are visible in the northern hemisphere, others in the southern hemisphere, and some can be observed from most of both hemispheres. The complete list consists of M42 Orion Nebula, M8 Lagoon Nebula, M17 Swan Nebula, Coal Sack Nebula, Large Magellanic Cloud, Small Magellanic Cloud, M31 Andromeda Galaxy, M81 Bode's Galaxy, M45 Pleiades, M44 Beehive Cluster, NGC 4755 Jewel Box, M7 Ptolemy's Cluster, NGC 5139 Omega Centauri, NGC 104 47 Tucana, M22 Sagittarius Cluster, and M13 Hercules Cluster.

The interest in this type of project and the use of catalogs allows many students to be introduced to the world of astronomy, taking into account the need to prepare the observation sessions in advance (Fig. 4 and 5).

Fig. 4 Preparing the observation, xxx Primary School in Beijing (Credit: Geya Zhu)

Fig. 5: Informational poster for the observation prepared for the "Messier Challenger" project in China. (Credit: Geya Zhu)

Conclusions

The "NGC for Schools without Telescope" catalog includes the 16 objects mentioned, along with their coordinates, image, sky map to locate them, a brief description of the object, as well as a short description of when it was first observed.

This contribution from the NASE program allows for showing different ways of approaching the teaching of science at various educational levels. It is a project that can be tackled in a general manner, as it does not require complex infrastructure or advanced instruments, and can be adapted to any space, country, or culture. It can be explored as deeply as the teacher or trainer in charge desires, and ultimately results in a collectively created product.

The detailed information in the catalog not only presents diffuse celestial objects but also includes part of their discovery and evolution history within the context of the universe. It enables exploration of topics in both natural and social sciences in general, providing synthetic information on distances, dimensions, and stages of evolution of the objects, showcasing the interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary nature of astronomy.

The catalog is available on the NASE website, where it can be freely downloaded, and constitutes an excellent citizen science proposal.

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